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The Autism Holiday: a 5 to 10 Minute Assisted Body-Language Recognition Training Method that 'Switches Off' Autistic State for 3 Days.

- Winworld Pty Ltd
Australia

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WORKING NOTES:

1. A two-day observation exercise (performance challenge-demand) to correctly identify passers-by mood from their body-language at approximately 35-100m proximal distance within approximately a 3 to 5 second time-window each, resulted in automatic emergence of a fast positive Promotional Regulatory Fit thinker-type behaviour frame.
2. Cognitive speed was significantly enhanced and body-language of the trainee changed (gait, posture, body-balance and physical flexibility) at the end of the second day brief-training session outside a local shopping mall.
3. Importantly the female trainer was an accomplished body-language reader (a top 1% performance salesperson) Promotional Regulatory Fit Thinker-type,

giving performance feedback at the end of each trial attempt.

4. Typical autistic knowledge memory access and 'depth' was unimpaired throughout the 3 days while all other noted above factors remained constant.

The training method is recommended for further experimental use given its high efficacy in such a brief training period. Of note: the male 45yo autistic trainee had an AQIS score of 38, and was Aspergian.

